

Valence instability in nano-form of EuPd_2Si_2 compound

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Abstract

EuPd_2Si_2 is a unique valence fluctuating system which exhibits cooperative and continuous valence transition at about 150K and has been extensively investigated [1]. We have prepared the compound EuPd_2Si_2 in nanocrystalline form by high-energy ball-milling technique. The compound is found to retain the ThCr_2Si_2 -type tetragonal structure while the average particle size decreases to less than 10 nm after a milling time of 2.5 hours. We report here detailed investigation of Eu valence state using the microscopic technique of Mössbauer spectroscopy. We find that the Mössbauer spectra of the nanocrystalline compound is divalent like at room temperature and becomes bimodal with lowering temperature unlike that of the parent compound. There is a progressive transfer of intensity from divalent like state to trivalent like state with decreasing temperature. In other words there appears to be a disorder broadened first order valence transition with decreasing temperature unlike for the bulk form. However, the transfer of intensity ceases below about 50K and a significant fraction reveals divalent state for Eu. A clear hyperfine splitting of the divalent component is observed at 4.2K, thereby confirming that the divalent like component ultimately orders magnetically below about 12K. Thus there is a qualitative change in the valence behavior in this compound as the particle size is reduced, which is reported for the first time for Eu based mixed valent compound. There are qualitative changes in the temperature dependent magnetic susceptibility as well.

Keywords : Nanomaterials, Valance fluctuations, Mössbauer spectroscopy

References:

- [1] E.V. Sampathkumaran et al., J. Phys. C14, L237 (1981).